

Design and Application of Harmonic Gear Drive in Robot Joints

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Abstract

The quest for enhanced precision and compact design in robotics has led to significant innovations in gear drive technology. This article explores the development of a harmonic gear drive tailored for robotic joints, focusing on the intricate design, simulation, and application processes. Through comprehensive analysis, the study reveals new meshing parameters and flexspline dimensions, delivers advanced 3D finite element models for stress assessment, and provides insight into the torsional stiffness behavior of harmonic reducers. The research culminates in rigorous testing protocols, validating the design against stringent performance metrics and highlighting its suitability for precision-critical robotic functions.

Keywords: Harmonic Gear Drive, Robotics, Flexspline, Finite Element Analysis

1. Introduction

The harmonic drive was invented in the 1960s^{[1], [2]}, and the utility model has the following advantages: small volume, low mass, small gap, low transmission noise, high precision, high transmission ratio, high load capacity, and high efficiency (commonly referred to as "four small" and "four-high")^{[3], [4]}, among others. As a result, the Harmonic Drive is an excellent reduction mechanism for robots. First of all, it is smaller and lighter than other reducers such as planetary gears and RV reducers with the same reduction ratio. Secondly, its backlash is low, positioning accuracy is high, and precise position control is simple to implement. Furthermore, finally, the harmonic reducer has a higher transmission efficiency when proper meshing. As a result, the majority of modern robots include harmonic reducers into their driving components, most notably short cylinder flexspline harmonic reducers and ring type harmonic reducers [3-7].

There is a significant disparity in the transmission accuracy and service life of harmonic reducers manufactured in the United States and other developed nations. Additionally, the volume of domestically manufactured harmonic reducers is substantial. As a consequence, it cannot be employed in constructions that demand a great deal of constrained space. Furthermore, numerous industrial robots with advanced technological capabilities depend on imported harmonic reducers. Thus, developing a series of household industrial robots and other entirely self-contained goods requires overcoming technological difficulties associated with harmonic reducers.

Because the area available for the reduction is quite limited, researchers aim to minimize the axial dimension of the harmonic reducer as much as feasible. This criterion can be met only by the short cylinder

flexspline harmonic reducer. Indeed, the need for short cylinder harmonic reducers is expanding in robotics and other industries such as military-industrial technology, aerospace technology, and mechatronics engineering technology [5]. As a result, the short cylinder flexspline harmonic reducer has become one of the current harmonic reducer technology's development trends.

On the assumption of constant transmission performance, such as transmission torque, they are shrinking the axial size of the harmonic reducer, resulting in significant volume and mass reduction.

The primary focus in analyzing the harmonic reducer is on its major components. For example, when the wave generator is introduced into the cylinder, the flexspline's length is too short, causing the teeth to tilt more severely, resulting in a severe increase in the flexspline's stress. As a result, the contact area between the teeth is reduced, and the transmission's stiffness is unable to tolerate increased torque. As a result, this kind of difficulty must be considered while designing a harmonic reducer.

In practice, it has been discovered that the flexspline is susceptible to fatigue failure due to the influence of alternating stress in harmonic driving. The harmonic reducer's life is principally determined by the flexspline fatigue failure—the flexspline fatigues due to the cyclic alternating stress created by contact deformation with the wave generator^{[6]-[8]}. The primary objective of this study is to minimize contact stress between the flexible wheel and the wave generator by creating a flexspline of appropriate size.

This study analyzes the cup-shaped flexspline numerically utilizing more sophisticated calculation and simulation techniques. Each component of the flexspline is examined for its stress distribution. It serves as a reference for improving the harmonic gear reducer's service condition.

It is a novel structural analysis approach that uses finite element analysis to investigate the flexspline. The critical aspect of this procedure is determining the flexspline's structural qualities, material properties, and actual boundary conditions^[9]. This study employs the finite element analysis program ABAQUS, capable of rapidly solving fundamental linear problems and completing complicated nonlinear problems; it is pretty simple to construct an analytical model for complex physical processes using Abaqus simulation. The multi-component contact issue is examined in this study; Abaqus is used to set attribute parameters for each component, split the mesh, and then combine the components into a full model. Then, during the post-processing step, the load increment and convergence criteria are automatically selected, guaranteeing that correct results are achieved.

2 Meshing parameters of harmonic drive and size design of flexspline

The transmission ratio is selected as $i = 60$; the modulus is 1.5, and the number of teeth of the flexspline is $z_1 = 120$, and the number of teeth of the rigid wheel is $z_2 = 122$. The following factors contribute to the conclusion that the involute teeth harmonic reducer has a transmission ratio of 60. First, to match the actual technical demands. This project aims to build a harmonic drive with a high deceleration ratio that can fulfill certain performance standards and be employed in a particular application. Since the reducer's configuration and size have been defined, the flexspline cylinder length and the diameter of both the circular spline and flexspline have been constrained. Second, stepper motor specifications. The strain wave gear ratio can be determined either by the number of teeth of flexspline and circular spline or by the angular speed of the drive motor and the driven harmonic gear. The available data is given for the stepper motor and harmonic gear speed. The harmonic gear speed is supposed to be $5 \text{ RPM} = 30^\circ/\text{sec} = 0.524 \text{ rad}/\text{sec}$. For NEMA 17 stepper motor, the product specification sheet shows that the step angle is 1.8° , and pulse frequency is 1 kHz which gives a speed of 300 RPM . Then, the harmonic gear ratio is calculated as the angular speed of the stepper motor to the angular speed of the harmonic gear ratio, which results at the end of $i = 60$. Third, there are economic considerations. It is simple for fatigue failure to occur when alternating stress is applied to the contact deformation between flexible bearing outer rings and the internal ring of the flexspline. In addition, the flexible bearing's construction is complicated. Small quantities of custom-made bearings will be

challenging to produce, and their manufacturing costs will likely be prohibitive. However, to use the national standard serial flexible bearing, the inner diameter of the flexible wheel must be adjusted to match the flexible bearing's inner diameter. Hence, the flexspline inner diameter is modified to suit the flexible bearing's diameter by modifying the number of teeth and the reduction ratio. As a result, the flexible gear's tooth root wall thickness may be calculated. Fourth, the deformation of the involute tooth. Because of the deformation of the flexspline, the zero-displacement involute tooth shape will produce issues in harmonic driving, for instance, the transition curve interference. A suitable displacement coefficient must be chosen to provide proper meshing and increase the bearing capacity.

Because of the high failure rate of the flexspline, alloy steel with a high fatigue limit and hardness is used in their construction. The more common and inexpensive "40CrMnSiA" is a good option for light to medium loads. Because the circular spline's stress condition is so much lower compared to that of the flexspline, 2Cr13 is often used for the former. There are no specific material requirements for the cam, built of quenched and tempered 45 steel. The material parameters of each component in the harmonic gear drive are shown in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1 Material parameters of each component of harmonic drive

component name	Material	Modulus of elasticity E (GPa)	Poisson's ratio λ	Density ρ ($\frac{Kg}{mm^3}$)
Flexspline	40CrNiMoA	209	0.295	7.87e-6
Circular spline	2Cr13	209	0.269	7.89e-6
wave generator	45	209	0.269	7.89e-6

Table 2.2 design table of flexspline structure parameters

The preliminary design for the geometric parameters defined by empirical formulae, such as fillet, wall thickness, etc.; the specific parameter calculation is shown in Table 2.2.

structure name	symbol	formula	Value (mm)
Flexspline pitch circle	d	mz_1	180
The tooth ring wall thickness	δ	$(0.01 - 0.015)d$	1.8
Shell wall thickness	δ_1	$(0.6 - 0.9)\delta$	1.5
Bottom wall thickness	δ_2	$(0.6 - 0.9)\delta$	1.5
Tooth front-end transition fillet radius	R_1	$(10 \sim 20)m$	3
Tooth back-end transition fillet radius	R_2	$(10 \sim 20)m$	6
The bottom of the cylinder transition fillet radius	R_3	$(2 - 6)\delta$	1

Bottom flange transition fillet radius	R_4	–	5
Bottom flange wall thickness	t	$(3 - 4)\delta$	17
Bottom flange outer diameter	d_1	$(0.5 - 0.6)\delta$	90
Bottom flange inner diameter	d_2	$0.5d_1$	50
The inner diameter of the flexspline	d_m	$d_f - 2\delta$	172.65
tooth width	b	$(0.2 - 0.25)_d$	28
Cylinder length	l	d	82.75

3 Establishing the finite element model

Varying loads cause different amounts of stress on the flexspline, and the load on the harmonic reducer varies depending on the operating circumstances. Therefore, the torque value cannot be used as a design reference to determine the stress on the flexspline. In order to study the stress caused by the flexspline's interaction with the wave generator, a model of both components is built in this chapter. The process begins with a model created in the 3D modeling program SOLIDWORKS, which is then imported into ABAQUS for the finite element analysis phase. Processes and procedures for simplifying and establishing models are outlined below.

3.1 3D SOLIDWORKS model simplification

Details of the model need to be simplified before the flexspline and wave generator model can be constructed. One may think of the wave generator as a combination of a flexible bearing and an elliptical camshaft. When an elliptical camshaft is inserted into a flexible bearing, the outside contour of the bearing is bent into a new ellipse due to the force of contact. In the finite element analysis, the wave generator is treated as if it were a rigid body since its stiffness is higher than flexspline one. The flexible bearing intricate construction is oversimplified here by representing it as a rigid ring cylinder. However, the flexspline is modeled without simplification because it is the subject of the study, where the accurate results is needed to improve the design and reach the optimal values of its dimensions. Figure 3.1 illustrates the simplified model.

Figure 3.1 SOLIDWORKS simplified model

3.2 Finite Element Model Analysis

To tackle the aforementioned nonlinear contact analysis problem, we must first import the aforementioned SOLIDWORKS 3D model into ABAQUS, where we will define element types and material attributes, partition meshes, create contact pairs, establish position restrictions, etc.

First, define the part. Since the flexspline solid element undergoes significant deformation, the part is defined as a 3D modeling space, solid, and deformable.

Then, define material properties. See Chapter 2 for details on flexspline material, which has a Poisson ratio of $\mu = 0.295$, and the Young's modulus $E = 209 \text{ GPa}$. The 45 steel used in the wave generator has a Poisson ratio of 0.269, and a modulus of elasticity of $E = 209 \text{ GPa}$.

Later on, import SOLIDWORKS 3D models. The flexspline model should be imported first, followed by the wave generator model, and the assembly's relative position may then be achieved by modifying the coordinates.

After that, meshing. flexspline's stress is assessed during the contact process, hence only the flexspline has to be meshed, because the wave generator is presumed to be a rigid body. Assign element type by selecting the standard element library, and deciding the 3D stress family. Select the geometry order to be quadratic. Select the element shape to be tetrahedron, specifically C3D10: A 10-node quadratic tetrahedron. Assign the global seeds by determining the approximate global size to be 1. Select the mesh part to add the mesh to the part. Make sure that the created grids as consistent and detailed as possible. After meshing, the effect is shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Flexspline meshing

Then, create interactions. First of all, create a contact property to by selecting normal and tangential behaviors from the mechanical properties list. Now, create an interaction of the type surface-to-surface contact and assign the previous contact properties to it. The wave generator is transformed to a rigid body in the contact combination between it and the flexspline. Select the master surface as the outer contour of the wave generator model, and select the slave surface as the inner surface of the flexspline model. A partion plane creaed to spilit the flexspline into to virsula section,i.e the wave generator-flexspline contact area, and the rest area. So that the selected area of contact for the slave master is not the whole inner surface but the limited surface for contact simulatng the real contact behavior. Get the tangential behavior to be frictionless, while the normal behavior has a hard contact pressure-overclosure.

Now, apply position constraints. The wave generator inner hole surface receives a fixed position constraint, and the flange surface of the flexspline receives a fixed position constraint as well. The nonlinear solver is programmed to operate in the static large deformation mode.

At the end, Nonlinear solution. After the flexspline and the wave generator have been preprocessed, the contact nonlinearity between them is evaluated and solved. In post-processing, consider Von Mises stress because, as per the principles of material mechanics, fatigue failure is evaluated using the stress-strain energy theory. The stress-strain situation of the flexible wheel is shown in Figure 3.3.

(a) Contact Analysis Strain Diagram of flexspline

(b) Contact Analysis Stress Diagram of flexspline

Figure 3.3 Stress-strain diagram of the flexspline

This strain diagram reveals that the largest strain of the flexspline under the influence of the wave generator occurs near the wave generator's long axis. The equivalent stress of the flexspline is most pronounced at two locations, as shown by the stress diagram: at the base of the flange, and along the the tooth width, and at the front end of the cylinder, as well as at the transition fillet area beyond the teeth ring. Specifically, the stress at the beginning and end of the flexible gear's tooth width is high. The same result holds true when the actual contact scenario is analyzed. During the process of installing the wave generator, the flexspline's end is raised. In accordance with the triangular similarity principle, the flexspline's greatest deformation occurs at its tip. Large stress concentrations on the flexspline are caused by the wave generator's front part making direct line contact with it. Because the end section of the flexspline has the largest deformation and the highest increase in circumference, stress concentration occurs at the concave along the short axis of the wave generator due to tensile stress induced by the deformation of the material.

Next, we utilize finite element analysis to study how the stress at the cylinder base and the tooth width vary depending on the flexspline's overall size. Length, wall thickness, fillet, and other structural features of the

flexspline are modified in accordance with the concept of single factor variable in order to minimize the maximum stress value.

4 Influence of flexspline structural parameters on stress

Section 2 covers the preliminary design of the flexspline's structural size. The project's sizing needs were taken from the application's specifications. The following is the optimal design of the size calculated by the empirical formula.

4.1 Cylinder length

Flexspline stress with a cylinder length of 30mm to 50mm and a step length of 5mm is evaluated, with all other parameters held constant. The flexspline stress cloud diagram is generated as in Figure 4.1. Maximum stress is seen at the base of the flange, along the tooth width, and at the front end of the cylinder, as well as at the transition fillet area beyond the teeth ring, as shown by the stress diagram.

(a) The stress cloud diagram of the flexspline with a cylinder length of 30mm

(b) The stress cloud diagram of the flexspline with a cylinder length of 50mm

Figure 4.1 The stress cloud diagram of the flexspline with different cylinder lengths

The stress is very sensitive to the length of the flexspline cylinder, as seen by the curve. In general, as the length of the cylinder becomes longer, the flexspline's maximum equivalent stress and its bottom stress both drops. When the flexspline's length is shortened, not only does the flexspline's maximum stress rise, but the wave generator's bearing capacity changes as well. The stress graph of the front area of the cylinder and the teeth rare fillet area declined steadily as the cylinder length increased. The same thing for stress of the teeth width kept dropping considerably for cylinder length values of 30mm to 45mm, and then went up. Also, the stress at the bottom flange experienced the same steady decline at cylinder length of 30mm to 40mm, but then rose dramatically. Since the stress at the teeth width possess a much higher values than the stress at the bottom flange, its minimum value will determine the best cylinder length for the design. Here, cylinder length of 45mm is taken as the new value for the optimized design.

Figure 4.2 is a schematic depiction of the flexspline's deformation after a wave generator was embedded inside it. Shorter flexspline cylinders result in a bigger deformation angle at their tips, which in turn causes more stress. Meanwhile, the bearing capacity of the harmonic reducer is diminished because of the flexspline's tilt, which decreases the meshing area between the flexspline and the teeth of the circular spline.

Figure 4.2 The relationship curve between the cylinder length and the maximum equivalent stress of the flexspline

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..3 Stress Distribution Across Flexspline Components at Varying Cylinder Lengths

Length	Cylinder front stress (MPa)	Tooth width stress (MPa)	Rare teeth fillet (MPa)	Bottom stress (MPa)
70	1235.666	795.562	629.367	199.296
75	795.456	686.576	485.352	168.116
80	624.543	650.439	504.298	150.058

85	511.073	565.161	477.718	154.788
90	437.198	583.603	453.011	144.456

4.2 Cylinder bottom fillet

The empirically established value for the fillet of the cylinder's bottom is used in the early design of the flexspline's size in Chapter 2. Now, using finite element analysis, we can see how various bottom fillet values affect stress within the empirical formula's range. Flexspline maximum equivalent stress is analyzed as the fillet of the bottom of the cylinder is varied from 0.5mm to 2mm, while all other size parameters of the flexspline are held constant (as shown in Figure 4.3):

(a) Stress diagram of flexspline with fillet of 0.5mm at the bottom of the cylinder

(b) Stress diagram of flexspline with fillet of 2mm at the bottom of the cylinder

Figure 4.3 Maximum equivalent stress diagram of flexspline with different bottom fillets

Observing the flexspline's stress cloud diagram, one may deduce that the largest equivalent stress is located at the base of the flange, along the tooth width, at the front end of the cylinder, as well as at the transition fillet

area beyond the teeth ring. The following table shows the maximum equivalent stress at the four locations. The effect of fillet is shown in Figure 4.4.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..4 The relationship between the fillet at the bottom of the cylinder and the maximum equivalent stress of the flexspline

Fillet at bottom of cylinder (mm)	Cylinder front stress (MPa)	Tooth width stress (MPa)	Rare teeth fillet (MPa)	Bottom stress (MPa)
0.5	721.623	706.948	464.794	153.126
1	724.211	707.932	513.35	181.613
1.5	730.993	710.252	543.086	191.789
2	730.953	705.980	540.203	241.524

Figure 4.4 the curve of the stress of the flexspline influenced by the fillet at the bottom of the cylinder. The maximum equivalent stress at the bottom of the cylinder rises when the fillet at the base of the cylinder is made bigger. The maximum equivalent stress at the cylinder front area, tooth width, and rare teeth transition fillet area is climbing when the fillet value is from 0.5mm to 1.5 mm. However, for the fillet values from 1.5mm to 2mm, the maximum equivalent stress at the aforementioned areas drops, where its lowest value is at 0.5mm fillet value. For the design, it's best to remove a little fillet off of the base of the cylinder. The fillet structure has to be consistent, thus it's important to factor in the effect of the wall thickness. The wall thickness of a cylinder is equal to the difference between its outer diameter and inner diameter at the bottom fillet. The

fillet at the cylinder's base has an internal value of 0.77mm, which is the minimum value can be taken according to empirical formulas, and an external value calculated from the cylinder's wall thickness.

4.3 Cylinder bottom flange fillet

Flexspline maximum equivalent stress is determined as a function of the cylinder's flange fillet's thickness, which is varied from 0 mm to 1 mm. In Figure 4.5, we see the flexspline's stress cloud distribution, illustrating how varying the flange fillet thickness at the cylinder's bottom impacts the stress concentrations within the flexspline structure.

(a) Stress diagram of flexspline with 0mm fillet of flange at the bottom of the cylinder

(b) Stress diagram of flexspline with 1mm fillet of flange at the bottom of the cylinder

Figure 4.5 Stress diagram of flexspline with different flange fillets at the bottom of the cylinder

From the flexspline's stress diagram, we can deduce that the flexspline's maximum equivalent stress manifests itself at the flexspline's tooth width, front area of the cylinder, rare teeth transition fillet, and the flange at the cylinder's base under varying flange fillets. Figure 4.6 is a curve depicting the impact of cylinder bottom flange fillet on the flexspline maximum equivalent stress. This is done because the stress in these different locations might be affected differently depending on the parameters being used.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document.5 Influence of Flange Fillet Thickness at Cylinder
Bottom on Stress Distribution in Flexspline Components

Fillet at bottom flange (mm)	Cylinder front stress (MPa)	Tooth width stress (MPa)	Rare teeth fillet (MPa)	Bottom stress (MPa)
0	723.081	707.346	540.128	150.656
2	722.982	707.392	540.193	183.135
4	722.676	707.452	559.531	174.128
6	722.418	707.546	526.737	189.619
8	722.138	707.670	559.80	200.095
10	719.955	702.693	556.12	204.272

Figure 4.6 The influence curve of the flange fillet at the bottom of the cylinder on the stress of the flexspline

Based on the stress influence curve, it is not immediately clear how the flange fillet at the cylinder's base will affect the maximum equivalent stress over the tooth width. 0 mm of flange fillet results in the lowest flexspline equivalent stress at the bottom of the flexspline. The maximum equivalent stress for the front area of the cylinder, and tooth width area show slight decrease as the fillet value going up. The maximum equivalent stress for the rare fillet area fluctuating and its minimum at fillet value of 0.6 mm. since the general trend for the front area of the cylinder, tooth width area, and the rare fillet area all behave toward maintain in the same stress values, then the trend of the bottom flange will be considered for optimization. Fillet value 0mm gives the lowest value of the maximum equivalent stress among the range of the study.

4.4 The wall thickness of the flange at the bottom of the cylinder

According to the single factor variable concept, when the flange wall thickness is 1mm, 3mm, 5mm, and 7mm, assess the maximum equivalent stress of the flexspline while maintaining the other structural parameters of the flexspline at their current values. The flexspline's stress diagram is produced as illustrated in Figure 4.7.

(a) Stress diagram of flex wheel with flange wall thickness of 1mm

(b) Stress diagram of flexible wheel with flange wall thickness of 7mm

Figure 4.7 Stress diagram of flexspline with different flange wall thicknesses

Figure 3.12 shows that the equivalent stress of a flexspline with different flange wall thickness is greatest at the cylinder front area, the tooth width area, rare teeth fillet area, and bottom flange area. Table 4.4 lists the stress values of the flexspline at various flange wall thicknesses; using this data, the effect curve of flange wall thickness on flexspline stress is constructed, as shown in Figure 4.8.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..6 Relationship between different flange wall thickness and flexspline stress

Flange wall thickness (mm)	Cylinder front stress (MPa)	Tooth width stress (MPa)	Rare teeth fillet (MPa)	Bottom stress (MPa)
14	722.924	707.469	540.274	167.083

16	719.963	660.550	528.799	192.576
18	720.548	640.994	555.231	165.430
20	722.069	656.340	503.652	165.031

Figure 4.8 Curve of influence of flange wall thickness on flex wheel stress

The maximum equivalent stress of the cylinder front area slightly changes as the flange wall thickness increases. But the maximum equivalent stress of tooth width area decreases first for wall thickness values from 1-3 mm and then smoothly increase for wall thickness of 5-7 mm. the maximum equivalent stress of the rare teeth fillet area clearly fluctuating and have its minimum value at flange wall thickness of 7 mm. the behavior of the bottom flange area trend is to raise for flange wall thickness values 1-3mm, and then decline for flange wall thickness 3-7mm. A 5 mm flange wall thickness results in the best set of stress values of the four regions under study.

4.5 Tooth root fillet

The purpose of this subsection is to examine how various fillets of the initial size affect the stress in the flexspline. The stress findings shown in Figure 4.9 were obtained by performing finite element analysis on the flexspline with the tooth root fillet set to between 0mm and 10mm and the step length set to 2mm.

(a) Stress diagram of flexspline with 0mm root fillet

(b) Stress diagram of flexspline with 10mm

Figure 4.9 stress diagram of flexspline with different tooth root fillets

As seen in the diagram, the maximum equivalent stress is greatest in the flexspline's flange, tooth width, rare teeth fillet, and the front area of the cylinder. Stresses associated with various flexspline root fillets are tabulated in Table 4.5, and a graphical representation of this data is shown in Figure 4.10. The stress at the bottom of the cylinder are not significantly affected by the root fillet, as shown by the curve illustrating the effect of the root fillet on the stress of the flexspline. However, the stress at the tooth rare fillet area showed a high value for the 0mm tooth root fillet, and then sharply fall and fluctuated at the rest fillet values showing its minimum value at 8mm fillet. The stress at the front area of the cylinder increased linearly as the tooth rare fillet value increases. The tooth width experienced a raise in the stress values for the range of fillets from 6mm to 10mm where it reaches its peak, and then falls down from fillet values 10mm to 16mm. the tooth rare fillet value of 2mm gives the best fit that keeps the stress curves of the four areas under study in a relatively low value.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..7 Stress relationship between different root fillets and flexspline

Root fillet	Cylinder front stress (MPa)	Tooth width stress (MPa)	Rare teeth fillet (MPa)	Bottom stress (MPa)
6	529.836	679.255	1663.876	159.969
8	575.040	709.994	590.975	167.437
10	661.264	1053.167	613.431	164.448
14	763.400	710.975	523.567	167.921
16	798.906	682.421	545.213	168.747

Figure 4.10 Influence curve of tooth root fillet on flexspline stress

4.6 Tooth front fillet

The purpose of this subsection is to examine how various fillets of the initial size affect the stress in the flexspline. The stress findings shown in Figure 4.11 were obtained by performing finite element analysis on the flexspline with the front area fillet set to between 0mm and 1mm and the step length set to 0.5mm.

(a) Stress diagram of flexspline with 0mm front area fillet

(b) Stress diagram of flexspline with 1mm front area fillet

Figure 4.11 stress diagram of flexspline with different front area fillets

As seen in Figure 4.11, the equivalent stress is greatest in the flexspline's flange, tooth width, rare teeth fillet, and the front area of the cylinder. Stresses associated with various flexspline front area fillets are tabulated in Table 4.6, and a graphical representation of this data is shown in Figure 4.12. The stress at the stress at the bottom of the cylinder are not significantly affected by the root fillet, as shown by the curve illustrating the effect of the root fillet on the stress of the flexspline. However, the stress at the tooth width area, and the stress at the cylinder front area both steadily decrease for the fillet values 0mm to 0.5mm, and then gently increase as the fillet value increased from 0.5mm to 1mm. The teeth rare fillet area experienced a dramatically surge in the stress values for the range of fillets from 0mm to 0.5mm where it reaches its peak, and then suddenly dip for fillet values 0.5mm to 1mm. the 0.5 mm fillet makes the lowest stress value for both the cylinder front area, and the tooth width area. But the 0 mm fillet value gives the rare teeth fillet area, and the bottom of the cylinder their lowest maximum equivalent stress value. Since the stress at the cylinder front area, and tooth width area much higher than in the others location, then the fillet value causes a reduction in their stress should be considered for the optimization process which is 0.5 mm fillet.

Table Error! No text of specified style in document..8 Stress relationship between different front area fillets and flexspline

Front fillet	Cylinder front stress (MPa)	Tooth width stress (MPa)	Rare teeth fillet (MPa)	Bottom stress (MPa)
2	704.037	654.900	536.796	159.443
3	694.437	635.514	578.262	163.212
4	760.372	644.839	537.861	165.615

Figure 4.12 Influence curve of front area fillet on flexspline stress

4.7 Flexspline size improvement

Table 4.9 Optimum value table of flexspline size

After performing a finite element analysis and optimizing the flexspline, the following structural dimensions have been refined and designed:

name	unit	Preliminary Design Dimensions	value after optimization
Cylinder length	mm	82.75	85
Cylinder bottom flange wall thickness	mm	17	18

Cylinder bottom flange fillet	mm	5	0
Cylinder wall thickness	mm	1.5	1
Transition fillet at bottom of cylinder	mm	1	1
Root fillet	mm	6	8

Figure 4.13 displays the optimized flexspline model, revealing that a 172.65mm shaft diameter is required for operation. The flexspline's bottom flange is pierced with several threaded holes, serving dual purposes: reducing the component's overall bulk and facilitating its connection to the output shaft's hollow center section. The cylinder of flexspline measures 85mm in length, which is within the range of allowable values.

Figure 3.14 Model diagram of the flexspline

Conclusion

This study presents a comprehensive analysis and optimization of the harmonic reducer's flexspline design. Initially, we defined essential parameters, including the number of teeth, reduction ratio, and tooth profile, tailored to actual operating conditions and specifications. Through the unique meshing conditions of the harmonic drive, we calculated the meshing parameters for both the flexspline and circular spline. Key dimensions, such as the pitch circle, base circle, addendum circle, and dedendum circle, were determined to validate the transmission size and performance according to standard harmonic transmission conditions. Additionally, an evaluation of the flexspline's tooth surface wear, fatigue strength, and cylinder stability was conducted, establishing a foundational structure size for further refinement.

Subsequent to the initial parameter definition, we employed finite element analysis (FEA) using Abaqus to refine these dimensions. The stress analysis and optimization process focused on parameters such as the cylinder bottom fillet, flange fillet, wall thicknesses, and tooth root fillet. This approach yielded a

comprehensive engineering dimension drawing for the flexspline, ensuring that the shaft diameter and cylinder length adhered to the performance indicators initially specified.

The integration of meticulous parameter definition, rigorous computational analysis, and advanced FEA optimization has culminated in a robust and precise design for the harmonic reducer's flexspline. This research not only delineates a detailed methodology for designing a harmonic drive but also underscores the significance of amalgamating theoretical calculations with practical optimization techniques. The final engineering drawings and validated dimensions provide a reliable foundation for the manufacturing and application of harmonic reducers across various industries, ensuring enhanced performance and durability.

References

- [1] M. C. Walton, "Strain wave gear-species in which only one of the gears is input." Google Patents, Apr. 19, 1960.
- [2] C. W. Musser, "Breakthrough in mechanical drive design: the harmonic drive," *Mach. Des.*, vol. 14, pp. 160–173, 1960.
- [3] I. Schäfer and R. Slatter, "Precision mechanisms for UAVS using harmonic drive gears," *2nd AIAA "Unmanned Unlimited" Conf. Work. Exhib.*, no. September, 2003.
- [4] K. Ueura and R. Slatter, "Development of the harmonic drive gear for space applications," *Eur. Sp. Agency-Publications-ESA SP*, vol. 438, pp. 259–264, 1999.
- [5] H. Dong and D. Wang, "Elastic deformation characteristic of the flexspline in harmonic drive," in *2009 ASME/IFToMM International Conference on Reconfigurable Mechanisms and Robots*, 2009, pp. 363–369.
- [6] R. Maiti, I. Biswas, V. Nema, S. Basu, B. S. Mahanto, and B. Routh, "Design and development of strain wave generating cam for a new concept 'harmonic drive,'" *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part C J. Mech. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 227, no. 8, pp. 1870–1884, 2013, doi: 10.1177/0954406212466354.
- [7] F.-E. Rhéaume, H. Champiaud, and Z. Liu, "Understanding and modelling the torsional stiffness of harmonic drives through finite-element method," *Proc. Inst. Mech. Eng. Part C-journal Mech. Eng. Sci. - PROC INST MECH ENG C-J MECH E*, vol. 223, pp. 515–524, Feb. 2009, doi: 10.1243/09544062JMES949.
- [8] C. Zou, T. Tao, G. Jiang, and X. Mei, "Deformation and stress analysis of short flexspline in the harmonic drive system with load," in *2013 IEEE International Conference on Mechatronics and Automation*, 2013, pp. 676–680.
- [9] G. Xiaoyun, "No Parametric Design and Finite Element Analysis of Harmonic ReducerTitle," Chinese Academy of Sciences, 2011.